

Improving assay feasibility and biocompatibility of 3D cyclic olefin copolymer microwells by superhydrophilic modification via ultrasonic spray deposition of polyvinyl alcohol

Akshaya Jagannath^a, Mingzhi Yu^a, Jiaqi Li^a, Nan Zhang^{a,b,*}, Michael D. Gilchrist^{a,b}

^a School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin, 4, Ireland

^b MiNAN Technologies Ltd., NovaUCD, Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Sample partitioning is a crucial step towards digitization of biological assays on polymer microfluidic platforms. However, effective liquid filling into microwells and long-term hydrophilicity remain a challenge in polymeric microfluidic devices, impeding the applicability in diagnostic and cell culture studies. To overcome this, a method to produce permanent superhydrophilic 3-dimensional microwells using cyclic olefin copolymer (COC) microfluidic chips is presented. The COC substrate is oxidized using UV treatment followed by ultrasonic spray coating of polyvinyl alcohol solution, offering uniform and long-term coating of high-aspect ratio microfeatures. The coated COC surfaces are UV-cured before bonding with a hydrophobic pressure-sensitive adhesive to drive selective filling into the wells. The surface hydrophilicity achieved using this method remains unchanged (water contact angle of 9°) for up to 6 months and the modified surface is characterized for physical (contact angle & surface energy, morphology, integrity of microfeatures and roughness), chemical composition (FTIR, Raman spectroscopy) and coating stability (pH, temperature, time). To establish the feasibility of the modified surface in biological applications, PVA-coated COC microfluidic chips are tested for DNA sensing (digital LAMP detection of CMV), and biocompatibility through protein adsorption and cell culture studies (cell adhesion, viability, and metabolic activity). Kidney and breast cells remained viable for the duration of testing (7 days) on this modified surface, and the coating did not affect the protein content, morphology or quality of the cultured cells. The ultrasonic spray coated system, coating with 0.25 % PVA for 15 cycles with 0.12 A current after UV oxidation, increased the surface energy of the COC (naturally hydrophobic) from 22.04 to 112.89 mJ/m² and improved the filling efficiency from 40 % (native untreated COC) to 94 % in the microwells without interfering with the biocompatibility of the surface, proving to be an efficient, high-throughput and scalable method of microfluidic surface treatment for diagnostic and cell growth applications.

1. Introduction

Although microfluidic point-of-care devices have simplified rapid testing of diseases, quantification of disease information remains a challenge [1–5]. In lateral flow and single-chamber reaction assays, fluorescent or colorimetric signal tracking occurs by monitoring the end result in one reaction chamber per sample, while in multiplexed assays,

multiple samples are analyzed simultaneously, but each sample is confined to one chamber without further compartmentalization [6,7]. To improve the quality of the information (including viral load quantification, presence or absence of mutations, coinfections, etc.) and assay throughput, it is necessary to partition the sample (nucleic acids or proteins) and the assay mix (including template nucleic acids, amplification enzyme, primers, and nucleotides) into multiple sealed

Abbreviations: PDMS, Polydimethylsiloxane; PMMA, Polymethyl methacrylate; COC, Cyclic olefin copolymer; PEG, Polyethylene glycol; PEO, Polyethylene oxide; PVA, Polyvinyl alcohol; LAMP, Loop mediated isothermal amplification; HCMV, Human cytomegalovirus; OWRK, Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble method; ATR-FTIR, Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; SEM, Scanning electron microscopy; CLSM, Confocal laser scanning microscopy; DAPI, 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole; HMDS, Hexamethyldisilazane; PFA, Paraformaldehyde; PCR, Polymerase chain reaction; BCA, Bicinchoninic acid protein assay; BSA, Bovine serum albumin; WCA, Water contact angle.

* Corresponding author at: School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin, 4, Ireland.

E-mail address: nan.zhang@ucd.ie (N. Zhang).

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microwells that can act as independent reaction chambers holding a fixed volume of liquid component. These microwells can then be individually analyzed for a signal on completion of an assay. 3-dimensional polymeric microwells present several challenges that hinder efficient partitioning and signal interpretation after assay: 1) bubble formation; 2) fluid leakage due to poor sealing; 3) contamination; 4) fouling of proteins or assay components due to low surface biocompatibility. Although automated microplate systems can uniformly dispense liquid in the wells through robotic sample handling, poor liquid-polymer interaction can result in inadequate filling and thus cause loss of throughput, poor signal detection and low functionalization capacity for niche applications [8–11]. Beyond point-of-care, the versatility of 3D microwells have allowed applications in nanoparticle-coated microbead synthesis for single-molecule detection [12], controlled growth of organoids for modelling diseases [13] and studying individual cell growth in active microenvironments through functionalization [14]. Thus, there is a need to understand and develop an easy-to-scale and stable 3-dimensional microwell system that readily partitions samples into fixed volumes for biological applications, not limited to but including diagnostics.

Historically, materials for microfluidic chips have undergone development from silicon and glass to polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and thermoplastics including polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and cyclic olefin copolymers (COC) [15]. COC is an ideal candidate for producing biocompatible and diagnostic 3D microwells due to the easily modifiable surface, higher glass transition temperatures (depending on the grade), lightweight, high transparency and better chemical/biocompatibility. This allows for easy detection and the thermoplastic characteristics help in microfeature fabrication with precision and micron-level accuracy. An inherent challenge of using untreated COC microfluidic chips is the inadequate hydrophilicity, particularly within the microwells, leading to insufficient liquid filling within each well and excess fluid flooding in the interstitial space between parallel channels and wells. The hydrophobic nature of the chip's surface renders it susceptible to non-specific protein adsorption when exposed to biological tissues or fluids [16]. Such phenomena can result in the clogging of microchannels and the disruption of fluid flow, thereby compromising the overall performance of the device. To address these challenges and enhance the precision of detection outcomes while extending the service life of microfluidic chips, it becomes imperative to modify the chip's surface by increasing its hydrophilicity. Furthermore, by increasing contact angle asymmetry between microchannels and surrounding regions, the force driving the liquid into the region of higher hydrophilicity reduces, thus rapidly allowing fluid flow within desired chambers and improved filling characteristics [17,18].

The hydrophilic modification of inherently hydrophobic polymers to improve fluid flow [19] and cell affinity [20,21] is widely documented. Oxidation of a polymer surface through plasma treatment or ultraviolet treatment does improve hydrophilicity [22,23] but the hydrophobic recovery is quicker due to the temporary nature of the oxidation that forms hydroxyl bonds on the surface. As concluded by Roy et al. [23], prolonged exposure to air after COC surface treatment with oxygen plasma resulted in increased contact angles after 17 days. Alternatively, coatings that can increase the surface energy of the substrate such as surfactants [24,25], PEG [26,27] and PEO [28,29] can be added but these interfere with DNA amplification assays or resist cell growth [30–34], limiting their applications despite suitable surface properties in point-of-care testing using microfluidics.

Recently, graphene oxide deposition has been used for selective altering of surface wettability or attaching biosensors for functionalization of COC [35,36]. Graphene oxide application in surface modification is due to its innate hydrophilicity and can be imparted to the COC surface upon deposition. Other advantages include increased nanoscale surface roughness, functionalization with hydroxyl groups, promoting enhanced wettability of the COC surface [37]. Combining plasma exposure and graphene oxide deposition, the contact angle was reported

to be reduced to 15° in one study [35]. However, long-term hydrophilicity and interference with diagnostic assays or cell attachment was not studied. Another possible disadvantage is the increased reports of toxicity of graphene oxide in the environmental sources which could pose a risk towards scalability of the method [38]. Thus, commercial viability of graphene oxide deposition as a method for surface treatment requires further investigation.

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is a hydrophilic charge-neutral polymer that has historically been used for reducing protein adsorption in silica capillaries, improving cell entrapment, immobilization and nucleic acid purification due to its low interference in amplification assays [39–41]. Previous studies that have used PVA-hydrogel for cell growth (skin wound healing PVA-composite film [42]; PVA-nanofiber hydrogel film for psoriasis treatment [43]) and anti-fouling (PVA-hydrogel ultrafiltration membrane [44]; PVA-grafted fabric membrane [45]; Semi-interpenetrated PVA-network [46]) applications have been established. However, the deposition of PVA through ultrasonic spray coating on an oxidized COC surface for a permanent hydrophilic change and its feasibility in biological applications has not been investigated previously. Ultrasonic spray coating is a new method which employs an ultrasonic generator to atomize coating solutions into small droplets which are then sprayed onto the substrate via a thin nozzle. This offers advantages over traditional dip or spin coating via controllable parameters to monitor the coating characteristics, such as desired thickness and throughput. Polymer substrates can be coated in parallel, thus improving the throughput of the process [47–49]. When an oxidized COC substrate is spray coated with a low concentration PVA solution, hydroxyl groups are formed on the surface which, when exposed under UV, leads to a permanent surface change. The ultrasonic spray coating of PVA on COC microwells combined with oxidation treatment to evaluate the increase in hydrophilicity has not been investigated. Moreover, it is hypothesized that the superhydrophilicity (water contact angle is <10°) is permanent when the spray coating is combined with UV treatment for oxidation and post-coating treatment due to the multifold increased surface energy. The increase in hydroxyl groups due to oxidation and PVA coating has a long-term effect on the surface wettability and exponentially increases microwell filling when bonded with a hydrophobic layer to create a large differential in surface energy between the well layer and sealing layer.

In this work, a COC-based microfluidic chip with a permanent superhydrophilic surface is developed by ultrasonic spray coating of low concentration polyvinyl alcohol onto oxidized cyclic olefin copolymer microwells and UV-treatment, followed by bonding with a hydrophobic adhesive surface to drive fluid filling into the wells. The combination of ultrasonic spray deposition to atomize PVA solution and UV/Ozone curing into a uniform and nanometer thick coat on the COC microwells for producing a superhydrophilic surface has been investigated. The applications of this surface have been studied comprehensively via interactions with biological components (proteins, cells and DNA) in a microwell environment. As proof of concept, a partitioned detection of CMV using an isothermal amplification method (LAMP) was performed and compared against quantitative PCR. This addresses the need for platforms for high resolution molecular assays (digital LAMP or PCR) disease detection. The ultrasonic spray coating conditions and fluid filling conditions are optimized to overcome filling and sealing challenges, followed by physical and chemical characterization of the coated surface as well as stability of the coating. The microfluidic substrate is then used for biosensing and cell culture applications to identify the extent of biocompatibility: a) digital loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) for detection of CMV, b) cell viability and adhesion, c) protein adsorption and d) metabolic activity during cell growth. This current study addresses the need for a long-term superhydrophilic surface suitable for versatile biomedical applications including diagnostics through improved filling behaviour and cell culture.

2. Materials and methods

Cyclic olefin copolymer (COC-8007) (TOPAS, Germany) pellets are used to produce the substrate material. The reagent used for surface treatment is a polyvinyl alcohol solution, which was made from PVA (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) powder. Isopropyl alcohol (IPA) solution used to clean the COC chips was from Merck. Deionized water was produced within the laboratory. Brilliant Blue FCF dye (1:100 dilution) from Sigma Aldrich and industry grade silicone oil (Lubrisolve) were used for the microwell filling experiments.

2.1. Ultrasonic spray coating of oxidized COC microfluidic chips and characterization of coated surface

Injection moulded microfluidic COC substrates (Supplementary) were oxidized using an Ossila UV/Ozone sterilizer for 15 min prior to ultrasonic spray coating (Cheersonic, China). 2 wt% of PVA (Polyvinyl alcohol) was prepared by adding 2 g of PVA powder to deionized water and stirring on a magnetic hot plate at 75 °C for 15 h. Other low-concentration solutions were obtained by dilution of 2 wt% PVA with MilliQ deionized water. The spray coating parameters are described in Table 1. Microfluidic chips were aligned with a 3D printed mask exposing only microwells and channels and mounted using a double-sided tape for ultrasonic spray coating. Spray coating cycles refers to the number of times the platform equipped with the microfluidic chip (to complete the vertical movement) and the nozzle (to complete the horizontal movement) cooperate to spray the entire platform (Fig. 1).

Surface wettability was characterized by measuring water contact angle (Ossila Contact Goniometer) at five regions on each coated surface and five samples coated under each spray condition and the arithmetic means taken for further analysis. Surface energy change before and after coating was determined using the Owens-Wendt-Rabel & Kaelble model (OWRK) due to its suitability for lower energy moderately polar surfaces while also being able to identify the polar and dispersive interactions between the liquids and the interface [50]. Three liquids with known dispersive and polar interactions were chosen: water, cyclohexane and chloroform and the contact angle were measured at least five times on each surface for one liquid (averaged after recording the measurements on five different chips) and plugged into the OWRK model (Equation 1) to calculate the surface energy before and after coating.

$$\frac{\sigma_l(\cos\theta + 1)}{2(\sqrt{\sigma_l^D})} = \left(\sqrt{\sigma_s^D}\right) \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_l^D}}{\sqrt{\sigma_l^D}} + \sqrt{\sigma_s^D} \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

where σ_l is the surface tension of the liquid having polar component σ_l^D and dispersive component σ_l^P ; σ_s^D , σ_s^P is the polar component and σ_s^D is the dispersive component of the surface tension of the solid. θ is the contact angle of the liquid with the surface.

To observe the microwell surface integrity, coating thickness and roughness parameters, optical light microscopy, and white light interferometry (NPFLEX Bruker) were performed on coated and uncoated samples for each spray condition. The spray coated COC samples (0.25 % PVA, 0.12 A current, 15 cycles) were analyzed using Raman spectroscopy (Scientific Xplora Plus, HORIBA) using a Nd:YAG laser with a laser wavelength of 1064 nm and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (Bruker). The main objective was to verify and confirm the presence of the coated polymer (PVA), functional groups and the

composition of the chemically modified layers. To investigate whether the coating was uniformly present on the microwells, 3D mapping using Raman spectroscopy was performed over a section of the coated wells to characterise the chemical composition distribution.

2.2. Assembly and evaluation of filling efficiency of PVA-modified COC microwells

Each PVA-modified COC chip was bonded to a hydrophobic (measured WCA $101 \pm 2.6^\circ$) acrylic medical grade pressure sensitive adhesive (ARCare 90106NB); this provided heat resistance to digital amplification temperatures, biocompatibility and use in diagnostics [51]. The bonded microfluidic assemblies were degassed in a vacuum pump for 15 min at 96.3 kPa before dye injection. To measure the improvements in microwell filling after surface modification, a syringe pump was connected to the inlet port to dispense 1:100 dilution of Brilliant Blue FCF dye (ThermoFisher) at a given flow rate (20-100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$), and silicone oil was manually injected in from the outlet port to seal the wells. The resulting wells were characterized by light microscopy (Fig. 2) to calculate the resulting filling efficiency of the chip. The experiments were repeated in triplicates for each flow condition variable (Table 2) while keeping other parameters constant at median values. Under positive pressure in a vacuum-treated chip, a very low flow rate was required to push the fluid into the channels where liquid then flooded the interstitial region above the microwells and filled each well through adhesion given the high surface energy of the modified wells. The silicone oil pushed out the remaining fluid in the interstitial region and sealed the region above the wells before observation.

2.3. Feasibility studies on the application of PVA-coated COC microfluidic chips

The loop-mediated amplification detection of human Cytomegalovirus from standard spiked plasma (viral load 30,000 IU/mL, Acrometrix) was performed to assess the in vitro diagnostic feasibility of the PVA-modified COC microfluidic chip [52]. The morphology of grown cells on the polymer surfaces was examined to investigate the quality of the formed cells. Kidney cell lines (HEK293) were chosen due to established studies documenting the versatile and high interest in these cells due to the wide range of conditions that can be treated by HEK293-derived biopharmaceuticals, including Virus-like particles (VLPs) for vaccine generation and viral vectors for cell and gene therapy [53]. For live cell staining, A549 (lung carcinoma epithelial cells) was used due to its high reproducibility, ease of cultivation and applications in anti-cancer drug selection studies and disease modelling [54–56]. Protein measurement from cells grown on a novel surface can be used as an indicator of good cell health if the total measured protein content does not change from protein measured using a known reference surface. In turn, this is used to identify whether a given surface is biocompatible or not, and in the present work, this was measured using cyclic-olefin copolymer (uncoated and sterilized) as a reference surface [57,58]. Cell viability was compared in the form of % live cells where the change in measured fluorescence was proportional to cell growth. This is a crucial biocompatibility metric that served to identify and establish the tolerance limits of the coating composition on the cells (cytotoxicity) (detailed protocols are provided in the Supplementary).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of PVA-coated COC surface

The results from the ultrasonic spray coating of PVA on oxidized COC microfluidic wells showed that both the increase in concentration of PVA in the coating solution and the number of spray cycles increased surface superhydrophilicity (water contact angle lower than 10°). However, when spray coating was done on native COC surfaces without

Table 1

Ultrasonic spray coating conditions.

Parameter	Values
PVA concentration	0.25 % / 0.5 % / 1 % / 2 % w/v
Spray coating cycles	10 / 15 / 20 / 30
Ultrasonic power	0.05 A / 0.12 A / 0.18 A
Pumping flow rate	0.05 / 0.1 / 0.5 / 1 mL/min
Nozzle height (fixed)	10.52 cm

Fig. 1. (A) Experimental set-up of ultrasonic spray coating device; (B) Fabricated microfluidic chip indicating coating area & microwell array and dimensions of individual microwell.

$$\text{Filling efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total filled wells (stage 1)}}{\text{Total formed wells (total wells - stage 4)}}$$

Fig. 2. Experimental set up of fluid injection and filling efficiency determination.

Table 2

Syringe pumping and flow conditions to test filling efficiency.

Surface modification method	only UV treatment/ only PVA spray coating/ PVA spray coating after UV oxidation and post-treatment
Inlet flow rate	20/ 30/ 50/ 100 μL/min
Vacuum degassing	96.3 kPa for 5/ 15/ 30/ 60 mins

UV-oxidation, the hydrophilicity was only reduced to $27 \pm 3.4^\circ$ and was not in the superhydrophilic range (Fig. 3A). Moreover, without UV treatment after coating, the hydrophilicity reduced with time as evidenced by the contact angles increasing closer to that of native uncoated COC. This could have been due to the increase in hydroxyl and carboxyl groups on oxidation [59], which not only would contribute to the hydrophilicity by increasing the surface energy but would also provide sites for the binding of polyvinyl alcohol on the coating. Five regions on

3 samples were analyzed for the presence of polyvinyl alcohol copolymer (Hit Quality Index >80 %) along with carboxylic acids and additional alcohols due to surface oxidation of cyclic olefin copolymer (Fig. 3B and 6C). This is consistent with previous research and FTIR results that display peaks at -OH absorption spectra. The detected weight ratio of the PVA copolymer was found to be 0.22 due to a concentration of the copolymer in the upper surface region while the bulk COC remained unmodified. The 3D mapping of the coated regions showed a combination of alcohols (hydroxyl groups), carboxylic acids, polyvinyl alcohols and ethers were present on the exposed layers that were chemically modified (see Supplementary Material). This is consistent with the hypothesized reaction that oxidation of the COC surface, followed by PVA coating, leads to an increase in hydroxyl and carboxylic acid groups, thus increasing surface polarity, and thus improving the hydrophilicity of the surface. The surface with the highest peak intensity in the -OH and -COOH group absorption spectra also had the highest surface energy, as determined by the OWRK model. The surface roughness increased with increasing % of PVA in the coating solution, which also contributed to hydrophilicity and produced a permanent superhydrophilic surface [60,61]. The surface texture changes, and uniformity of coating were analyzed using SEM, CLSM and white light interferometry. The depth characteristics of the coated microwells under CLSM revealed that the coating did not affect the filling volume. This could be due to the permanent chemical modification of the exposed COC layers from the ultrasonic spray coating process, rather than a thick film-like deposit. This resulted in the modified textural properties due to the coating deposition being in the nanometer range where roughness (S_a) was found to be $0.497 \mu\text{m}$ (see Supplementary material). With increase in concentration of PVA solution from 0.1 % to 2 %, the water contact angle reduced from 90° (native COC) to 5.6° . Thus, the coating parameters were optimized by means of oxidation and a post-treatment step to achieve long-term hydrophilicity.

It can be observed from Fig. 4 that hydrophilicity increased with an increase of the spraying cycle times. With 10 cycles, a total of 0.5 mL coating solution was sprayed onto the chip surface, which may not have been sufficient to cover the entire exposed surface area and would have produced a much lower coating thickness. Moreover, as the PVA concentration increased, a higher cycle time was needed to achieve a uniform and thicker coating on the surface in order to produce a superhydrophilic surface after curing. A PVA concentration >5 % resulted in dense droplets causing white spots on the microwell surface which are not desirable as they could interfere with downstream processes, such as imaging and detection. At a concentration of 0.25 wt%, the hydrophilicity of the chip was also increased greatly, with the water contact angle reducing to about 5° and surface energy increasing to $112.89 \pm 7.18 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ (Table 3). With maximum achievable free surface energy of the solid substrate, the ability of the liquid droplet to spread

Fig. 3. Characteristics of PVA-spray coated COC microwells: (A) Average contact angle is lowest when spray coating is combined with UV treatment; (B) ATR-FTIR of PVA-coated surface showing increasing number of OH groups with increased PVA%; (C) Raman Spectroscopy confirming PVA presence in the microwells; (D) SEM images of microwells surface before and after spray coating; (E) Depth profile of coated microwells using CLSM; (F) Increase in surface roughness after PVA modification.**.

more easily is maximized, thus supporting the superhydrophilic state of the surface [62]. This reached a steady state after about a month, and remained close to 9°, which confirms that this PVA treatment is stable for long time periods. In addition, when the PVA concentration is 0.5 wt %, the hydrophilicity of the chip can also be increased greatly, although compared with the PVA concentration of 0.25 wt%, the decrease of the contact angle is not uniform and the microwells appear overcoated (reducing the volume available for filling), which means that the spraying of PVA and UV / Ozone on the groups on the surface reached saturation. UV/ozone surface treatment can achieve low-temperature bonding between PMMA and COC microfluidic substrates through the formation of oxidized surfaces increasing surface polarity and thus increasing surface energy, allowing for easy wettability [22]. However, the water contact angle of the solely UV-treated surface is much lower than that of the combined PVA-UV treated surface. Long term superhydrophilicity requires a very highly polar surface with both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups, and the presence of alcohol permanently cured on

the surface layer of the COC provides this polarity. The stability and ageing effects of the spray coated surface were studied under varied pH, temperature, and time conditions. It was observed that in extremely acidic conditions, the PVA groups on the surface were destabilized, which caused an increase in water contact angle and a reduction in hydrophilicity. The surface remained stable from a weak acidic pH of 4.0 to a highly alkaline pH of 12. While this could be seen as a shortcoming of the surface, it can be useful for medical requirements since highly acidic conditions are not favourable in either biological or medical applications. With heat conditions, the surface coating remained stable from a frozen temperature to a surface temperature of 70 °C. Above this, the microwells started to deform as temperatures approached the glass transition temperature of 78 °C. However, the surface coating remained intact, and the water contact angle of the warped surface remained unaffected at these higher temperatures. The surface was also found to be stable for up to 6 months with a fluctuation of around 4.4° in the water contact angle.

Fig. 4. Stability of superhydrophilic coating at 0.25 % w/v PVA concentration**, 15 cycles and 0.12 A: Wetting conditions remain unchanged with time up to 30 days after which there is an increase in WCA >10°. Acidic pH greatly affects the stability of the coating due to the excess H⁺ ions added to the modified surface containing more OH⁻ groups from the PVA. At higher temperatures the warping effects of the polymer can destabilize the microwells form leading to greater perceived WCA.

Table 3

Surface energy changes after coating of COC microwells under different conditions**.

Surface treatment	Water Contact Angle	Surface energy in mJ/m ² (OWRK)
None (Native TOPAS COC 8007)	99.5 ± 3.8°	22.04 ± 4.64
Only PVA treated (no UV)	26.1 ± 2.5°	101.02 ± 14.92
0.25 % PVA-COC-UV	5.6 ± 1.4°	112.89 ± 7.18
2 % PVA-COC-UV	9.4 ± 1.6°	108.45 ± 6.21

** All tests were repeated in triplicates and tested as 5 batches on different days for reproducibility ($p < 0.05$).

3.2. Filling conditions and evaluation of filling efficiency changes

With higher concentrations of PVA (above 1 %), despite the lower water contact angle, the filling efficiency was found to be lower than surfaces coated with <1 % of PVA. This could have been due to the changed surface conditions having higher roughness and a thicker coating due to the greater PVA% in the coating solution, which could have contributed to the poor filling efficiency by not providing a full well volume for the liquid to fill. The ideal coating composition was found to be 0.25 % for 15 cycles (.

Fig. 5). Similar observations were noted with increasing numbers of spray coating cycles, while surfaces coated for >30 cycles were found to have poor filling ratios. For lower numbers of spray cycles, the coating was not sufficient and uniform to produce the surface energy conditions required for superhydrophilicity. Under the ideal conditions of 0.25 %

Fig. 5. Effect of low concentration PVA and spray coating cycles on water contact angle show an ideal long-term concentration of 0.25 % w/v and 15 cycles PVA for a stable superhydrophilic coating: (A) 0.1 % w/v (B) 0.25 % w/v (C) 0.5 % w/v (D) Comparison at median cycle number (15 cycles); (E) Light microscope visualization of filled wells indicate 2× increase in efficiency after PVA coating with UV treatment at 0.25 % ($p < 0.05$).

w/v PVA and 15 cycles, the filling efficiency increased to $94 \pm 4.1\%$, doubling the rate at which a microwell would fully fill. The superhydrophilic nature of the microwells drives the movement of water-based dyes into the wells preferentially, as the surrounding regions and top layer are hydrophobic. This is consistent with previous research that documented the preferential movement of liquids to regions of higher wettability [63–66].

The filling conditions of the liquid also played an important role in the filling efficiency of the microwells. With lower flow rates ($< 50 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$), the filling efficiency increased while the volume of liquid flowing out of the waste collection port reduced. A lower flow rate ensured proper (i.e., smooth and laminar) contact between the liquid dye and the coated wells without causing air bubbles to be introduced by turbulent contact conditions. This also maintained the degassed nature of the wells. Vacuum degassing for 15 min was found to be sufficient to vent the microfluidic chips; longer times did not cause any significant difference in the filling efficiency.

3.3. Feasibility studies

3.3.1. dLAMP detection of Cytomegalovirus on PVA-modified COC microwells

The detection of CMV (viral load around $10^5 \text{ IU}/\text{mL}$) was performed by filling the 0.25 % PVA coated wells with mastermix containing the fluorescent-tagged primers, enzyme, and template DNA. As seen in Fig. 6 A, the mastermix is partitioned into individual wells and the heating of these wells generates a signal through a positive amplification reaction. By recording the intensity of the fluorescent signal of each well

and plotting the intensities against well number, the viral load of the assay can be calculated. Here, to prove the concept of using PVA coated wells, a standard HCMV sample (viral load 30,000 IU/mL) was used as template for the LAMP assay. The distribution of the signal intensity between the wells included strong and weak positive, and negative wells. Although the wells were vacuum treated before mastermix injection, bubbles were seen in a few wells which could affect subsequent image analysis. This may have been due to the heating process generating air bubbles from within the liquid mastermix. When compared to the uncoated COC, however, it was observed that not only were the wells filled more effectively, allowing complete partitioning of the liquid sample, but also the amplification time reduced significantly. In the uncoated COC, the liquid sample did not fill the wells and instead occupied channels and interstitial spaces, due to which the amplification reaction was not uniform, thus increasing the total reaction time required for the assay to generate a fluorescent signal through the sample completely. The assay heating temperature is crucial to the design of the amplification process due to the low glass transition temperature of the COC 8007 substrate ($T_g = 78^\circ\text{C}$). At low heating temperatures, the amplification time was found to be almost an hour (time taken to achieve maximum and complete fluorescence), which was more than double that of a conventional LAMP assay in a thermocycler. At 62°C , the amplification in the microwells took the least total time to reach highest fluorescence intensity, although some wells remained only weakly positive or negative despite being filled. This could have been due to improper heat distribution in the wells as a result of having used a hot plate instead of a custom-built heating coil with a thermal sensor. This could also be a reason why the amplification time was not less than

Fig. 6. dLAMP detection of CMV on 0.25 % PVA coated COC microwells: (A) $10\times$ view of positive wells under fluorescent microscope after amplification reaction; (B) Comparison of amplification time between coated, uncoated and conventional thermocycler reaction showing significant time reduction in 0.25 % coated wells; (C) Temperature optimization for assay contributed to the amplification time reduction.

that when using a conventional thermocycler, even though a significant improvement was seen when compared to the uncoated (native) COC microwells.

3.3.2. Cell adhesion and viability of HEK293 and A549 adhered cells on PVA-modified COC surface

The morphology of 48 h cultured cells was observed under SEM on various regions of the PVA-coated COC substrates. As the amount of PVA in the coating composition increased, it was observed that the cells tended to cluster more and form film-like structures on the surface, and single cells were harder to identify (Fig. 7A). At 0.25 % PVA, both clustering cells on the flat regions and isolated cells in the microwells were observed. As PVA% increased, the surface roughness also increased multifold, leading to easier formation of cell clusters, while single cells were fewer in number and harder to locate in the microwells [67,68]. Additionally, enhancing the hydrophilic properties of COC increases cell spreading and adhesion [69]. The cell viability was observed by staining using DAPI/Rhodamine, which stains the actin and nucleus respectively. Healthy viable cells take up both the dyes and a clear boundary is observed between the nucleus and membrane regions, while partially alive or unhealthy cells may still take up the dyes, but the boundaries are diffused and not distinct. At lower concentrations of PVA (0.1 and 0.25 %), cells grown were healthy, greater in number (by visual observation) and supported cell growth since dividing cells were also seen. However, at higher concentrations of PVA, cells appeared to be viable but unhealthy as boundaries between nuclei and cell membranes were not distinctly clear. This indicates there is a threshold for surface modification beyond which the growth of the cells is affected but not completely hindered. With increasing carboxylic and hydroxyl groups

on the surface, the surface becomes increasingly negatively charged, inhibiting the growth of cells [70,71]. Thus, the application of PVA-coated COC substrates for cell studies requires a balance of hydrophilic and wettability of the surface against the increasing negative charges affecting the polarity and subsequently the growth characteristics of the cells. This ideal condition is provided by the 0.1 % and 0.25 % PVA coated cells.

3.3.3. Metabolic activity and protein content of HEK293 cells on PVA-modified COC

The total protein content in cells grown on polymeric surfaces is measured using BSA (bovine serum albumin) absorption as calibration standard (Supplementary). As seen in Fig. 8A, cells grown on the PVA-coated COC surfaces did not vary in their total protein content when compared to the uncoated (native) sterilized COC surfaces, which is a known biocompatible surface [57,72,73]. A 30 % increase in protein content was observed using 0.5 % PVA coated chip, due to the higher number of cells, as observed from the SEM images of cell culture films formed on the surface (Fig. 7A). This indicates that the ultrasonic spray coating of PVA combined with UV curing maintains the superhydrophilic nature of the surface to enhance cell spreading and adhesion without interfering in protein activity. However, since total protein content is not sufficient to determine whether the cells are healthy and viable for a prolonged period, such as is typically required for studying cell growth, AlamarBlue reduction assay was performed. As seen in Fig. 8B, the number of live cells reduced for surfaces with PVA concentrations >0.25 % after day 4, indicating the need to consider the cytotoxic threshold of coating below which cells are healthy and viable. Comparing the cell protein content and AlamarBlue reduction results,

Fig. 7. Cell morphology and viability of kidney and breast cell lines on PVA-modified COC microwells: (A) SEM imaging of changes in HEK293 cell adhesion with increase in PVA % in coating composition; (B) DAPI/Rhodamine staining of 48 h cultured A549 cells on 0.25 % PVA-modified COC; (C) Cell clusters on the microchannels; (D) Dividing cells in the microwells indicate coating does not inhibit cell growth.

Fig. 8. Measured protein content and live cells (as a function of metabolic activity) of HEK293 cells grown on PVA-modified COC: (A) Total protein concentration of cells cultured on various PVA% coated surfaces does not change when compared to control (native COC); (B) Live cell count reduces when PVA% increases above 0.25 %.

the 0.25 % PVA coating was the most stable for increased cell viability and non-inhibitory effects on protein activity for a sustained period of time (up to 7 days).

4. Conclusions

This study proposes a feasible alternative surface through PVA modification of an oxidized cyclic olefin copolymer substrate by turning it from hydrophobic to superhydrophilic for the effective filling of microwells. Furthermore, as droplets are atomized via ultrasonic energy, the coating process can be extended to any scale of microfeature dimensions not limited to microwells. By using ultrasonic spray coating at 0.12 A current and 0.25 % PVA concentration, a stable superhydrophilic surface can be created with a maximum water contact angle of $7.3 \pm 1.7^\circ$ for up to 30 days; this increases the surface energy from 22.04 to 112.89 mJ/m². This method can be automated and standardized using optimized parameters for ultrasonic deposition, thus minimizing human error, and maintaining the coat thickness range for maximum liquid filling.

The modified surface was investigated for chemical (functional group) and physical characteristic changes in the coated microwells against the native COC substrates, and the mechanism of improved superhydrophilicity was studied. The distribution of hydroxyl (alcohol) including the polyvinyl alcohol copolymer and carboxylic groups were observed on the ultrasonic spray coated microwells, confirming that uniform chemical composition was achieved using this method without affecting the free volume for filling, as observed in the depth profile. The simple process of UV curing following the spray deposition ensures a coat of uniform thickness in the nanometer scale on COC microwells for producing a superhydrophilic surface (WCA < 10°). While PVA coats have been used to induce hydrophilicity, by curing the wet-PVA droplets on the oxidized microwells under UV, permanent modification has been made to the polymer substrate, thus improving the extent of hydrophilicity and the longevity of this surface. This surface has been characterized using Raman spectroscopy for proof of substrate modification, and ideal conditions of PVA concentration, UV oxidation and curing time, number of cycles of ultrasonic spray coating and filling conditions have been identified for maximizing favourable interaction between the polymer microwell interface and biological liquids. Liquid partitioning in microwells coated with 0.25 % PVA improves from a filling efficiency of <50 % on a native COC substrate to around 95 %, allowing for ease in performing a digital LAMP assay for rapid point-of-care applications. Amplification time required for the detection of CMV using the coated microwells was found to be 21 min at an assay temperature of 62 °C. Heating played an important role in the complete amplification process

and is necessary to optimize during point-of-care applications of surface modified polymer substrates. The effect of the surface modification on cell growth and adhesion was studied in detail. The superhydrophilic modification resulted in increased cell adhesion and spreading (film formation) with non-inhibitory effects on protein content. However, with increasing PVA % (over 0.25 %), the cytotoxicity of the modified substrate increased and reduced the live cells % during the 7-day period. Thus, 0.25 % PVA (15 cycles at 0.12 A) coating was found to be the most suitable for long term stable superhydrophilicity, improving filling efficiency for point-of-care microfluidics and cell growth applications.

This study provides a repeatable and reproducible, stable polymer surface for biomedical applications. The use of ultrasonic deposition of PVA combined with UV drying can present as an easy to implement, flexible patterning method to selectively functionalize regions on a substrate. In case of the current study, the example of using a 3D printed mask for selective deposition of atomized PVA through spray coating, followed by UV drying in an enclosed chamber, ensures that the microwells are selectively modified to become superhydrophilic. For facile patterning of any general surface, the ultrasonic spray deposition method and UV curing can be combined with lithography as a pre-treatment step, or after injection moulding of thermoplastics as a post-treatment step for functionalization of polymeric substrates. The commercial viability of a superhydrophilic modified surface depends on the interplay of modification method (for long-term stability of surface), filling conditions for 3D structures and assay parameters. Thus, these parameters have been identified to employ this surface for a one-pot disease detection or modelling system. Future studies will include the investigation of these surfaces for integrated microfluidic point-of-care devices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Akshaya Jagannath: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mingzhi Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jiaqi Li:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nan Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Michael D. Gilchrist:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] A.M. Thompson, A. Gansen, A.L. Paguirigan, J.E. Kreutz, J.P. Radich, D.T. Chiu, Self-digitization microfluidic chip for absolute quantification of mRNA in single cells, *Anal. Chem.* 86 (24) (2014) 12308–12314.
- [2] M.I. Mohammed, S. Haswell, I. Gibson, Lab-on-a-chip or Chip-in-a-lab: challenges of commercialization lost in translation, *Procedia Technol.* 20 (2015) 54–59.
- [3] A. Thompson, A. Paguirigan, J. Kreutz, J. Radich, D. Chiu, Microfluidics for single-cell genetic analysis, *Lab Chip* 14 (17) (2014) 3135–3142.
- [4] A. Jagannath, H. Cong, J. Hassan, G. Gonzalez, M.D. Gilchrist, N. Zhang, Pathogen detection on microfluidic platforms: recent advances, challenges, and prospects, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics: X* 10 (2022) 100134.
- [5] S. Lei, S. Chen, Q. Zhong, Digital PCR for accurate quantification of pathogens: principles, applications, challenges and future prospects, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 184 (2021) 750–759.
- [6] Y. Chen, S. Qian, X. Yu, J. Wu, J. Xu, Microfluidics: the propellant of CRISPR-based nucleic acid detection, *Trends Biotechnol.* 41 (4) (2023) 557–574.
- [7] B. Ince, M.K. Sezginürk, Lateral flow assays for viruses diagnosis: up-to-date technology and future prospects, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 116725 (2022).
- [8] P. Slepíčka, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, Z. Kolská, V. Švorčík, Surface modification of polymer substrates for biomedical applications, *Surface Modification of Polymers: Methods and Applications* (2019) 399–426.
- [9] C. Zhang, D. Xing, Miniaturized PCR chips for nucleic acid amplification and analysis: latest advances and future trends, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 35 (13) (2007) 4223–4237.
- [10] A.A. Kojabad, M. Farzanehpour, H.E.G. Galeh, R. Dorostkar, A. Jafarpour, M. Bolandian, M.M. Nodoshan, Droplet digital PCR of viral DNA/RNA, current progress, challenges, and future perspectives, *J. Med. Virol.* 93 (7) (2021) 4182–4197.
- [11] S. Padmanabhan, J. Han, I. Nanayankara, K. Tran, P. Ho, N. Mesfin, I. White, D. DeVoe, Enhanced sample filling and discretization in thermoplastic 2D microwell arrays using asymmetric contact angles, *Biomicrofluidics* 14 (1) (2020).
- [12] W. Wang, C. Yang, X.Q. Cui, Q.L. Bao, C.M. Li, Droplet microfluidic preparation of Au nanoparticles-coated chitosan microbeads for flow-through surface-enhanced Raman scattering detection, *Microfluid. Nanofluid.* 9 (2010) 1175–1183.
- [13] P. Kakni, R. Hueber, K. Knoops, C. López-Iglesias, R. Trukenmüller, P. Habibovic, S. Giselbrecht, Intestinal organoid culture in polymer film-based microwell arrays, *Advanced Biosystems* 4 (10) (2020) 2000126.
- [14] S.-H. Kim, G.H. Lee, J.Y. Park, Microwell fabrication methods and applications for cellular studies, *biomedical, Eng. Lett.* 3 (2013) 131–137.
- [15] K. Ren, J. Zhou, H. Wu, Materials for microfluidic chip fabrication, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 46 (11) (2013) 2396–2406.
- [16] J.-N. Klatt, T. Hutzenlaub, T. Subkowski, T. Müller, S. Hennig, R. Zengerle, N. Paust, Blocking protein adsorption in microfluidic chips by a hydrophobin coating, *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* 3 (7) (2021) 3278–3286.
- [17] S. Wang, N. Yu, T. Wang, P. Ge, S. Ye, P. Xue, W. Liu, H. Shen, J. Zhang, B. Yang, Morphology-patterned anisotropic wetting surface for fluid control and gas-liquid separation in microfluidics, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 8 (20) (2016) 13094–13103.
- [18] M. Li, J. Hao, H. Bai, X. Wang, Z. Li, M. Cao, On-chip liquid manipulation via a flexible dual-layered channel possessing hydrophilic/hydrophobic dichotomy, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (15) (2023) 19773–19782.
- [19] T. Cubaud, U. Ulmanella, C.-M. Ho, Two-phase flow in microchannels with surface modifications, *Fluid Dynamics Research* 38 (11) (2006) 772.
- [20] S.K. Nemani, R.K. Annavarapu, B. Mohammadian, A. Raiyan, J. Heil, M.A. Haque, A. Abdelaal, H. Sojoudi, Surface modification of polymers: methods and applications, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 5 (24) (2018) 1801247.
- [21] M. Jurak, A.E. Wiącek, A. Ładniak, K. Przykaza, K. Szafran, What affects the biocompatibility of polymers? *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 294 (2021) 102451.
- [22] C. Tsao, L. Hromada, J. Liu, P. Kumar, D. DeVoe, Low temperature bonding of PMMA and COC microfluidic substrates using UV/ozone surface treatment, *Lab Chip* 7 (4) (2007) 499–505.
- [23] S. Roy, C. Yue, Y. Lam, Influence of plasma surface treatment on thermal bonding and flow behavior in cyclic olefin copolymer (COC) based microfluidic devices, *Vacuum* 85 (12) (2011) 1102–1104.
- [24] P. De Gennes, Interactions between polymers and surfactants, *J. Phys. Chem.* 94 (22) (1990) 8407–8413.
- [25] F.M. Michael, M. Khalid, R. Walvekar, H. Siddiqui, A.B. Balaji, Surface modification techniques of biodegradable and biocompatible polymers, biodegradable and biocompatible polymer composites: processing, properties and applications; Shimpi, NG, Ed (2018) 33–54.
- [26] V. Takke, N. Behary, A. Perwuelz, C. Campagne, Surface and adhesion properties of poly (ethylene glycol) on polyester (polyethylene terephthalate) fabric surface: effect of air-atmospheric plasma treatment, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 122 (4) (2011) 2621–2629.
- [27] M.K. Kim, I.S. Park, H. Dal Park, W.R. Wee, J.H. Lee, K.D. Park, S.H. Kim, Y.H. Kim, Effect of poly (ethylene glycol) graft polymerization of poly (methyl methacrylate) on cell adhesion: in vitro and in vivo study, *J. Cataract Refract Surg* 27 (5) (2001) 766–774.
- [28] K. Pandiyaraj, A.A. Kumar, M. RamKumar, P. Padmanabhan, A. Trimukhe, R. Deshmukh, P. Cools, R. Morent, N. De Geyter, V. Kumar, Influence of operating parameters on development of polyethylene oxide-like coatings on the surfaces of polypropylene films by atmospheric pressure cold plasma jet-assisted polymerization to enhance their antifouling properties, *J. Phys. Chem. Solid* 123 (2018) 76–86.
- [29] D.J. Eyckens, J.D. Randall, F. Stojcevski, E. Sarlin, S. Palola, M. Kakkonen, C. Scheffler, L.C. Henderson, Examining interfacial interactions in a range of polymers using poly (ethylene oxide) functionalized carbon fibers, *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 138 (2020) 106053.
- [30] L.J. White, A.J. Taylor, D.M. Faulk, T.J. Keane, L.T. Saldin, J.E. Reing, I. T. Swinehart, N.J. Turner, B.D. Ratner, S.F. Badylak, The impact of detergents on the tissue decellularization process: a ToF-SIMS study, *Acta Biomater.* 50 (2017) 207–219.
- [31] C.E. McNamee, S. Yamamoto, K. Higashitani, Effect of the physicochemical properties of poly (ethylene glycol) brushes on their binding to cells, *Biophys. J.* 93 (1) (2007) 324–334.
- [32] M. Stangl, A. Veerappan, A. Kroeger, P. Vogel, D. Schneider, Detergent properties influence the stability of the glycoprotein a transmembrane helix dimer in lysophosphatidylcholine micelles, *Biophys. J.* 103 (12) (2012) 2455–2464.
- [33] G. Liu, Y. Li, L. Yang, Y. Wei, X. Wang, Z. Wang, L. Tao, Cytotoxicity study of polyethylene glycol derivatives, *RSC Adv.* 7 (30) (2017) 18252–18259.
- [34] C. Schrader, A. Schielke, L. Ellerbroek, R. John, PCR inhibitors—occurrence, properties and removal, *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 113 (5) (2012) 1014–1026.
- [35] F. Dawaymeh, Y. Abbas, M. Khaleel, A. Alazzam, N. Alamoody, Tuning the surface wettability of cyclic olefin copolymer by plasma treatment and graphene oxide deposition and reduction, *Polymers* 13 (14) (2021) 2305.
- [36] S. Shahriari, M. Sastry, S. Panjikar, R. Singh Raman, Graphene and graphene oxide as a support for biomolecules in the development of biosensors, *Nanotechnol. Sci. Appl.* (2021) 197–220.
- [37] V. Nebol'Sin, V. Galstyan, Y. Silina, Graphene oxide and its chemical nature: multi-stage interactions between the oxygen and graphene, *Surfaces and Interfaces* 21 (2020) 100763.
- [38] A.N. Ghulam, O.A. Dos Santos, L. Hazeem, B. Pizzorno Backx, M. Bououdina, S. Bellucci, Graphene oxide (GO) materials—applications and toxicity on living organisms and environment, *Journal of Functional Biomaterials* 13 (2) (2022) 77.
- [39] S. Muppalaneni, H. Omidian, Polyvinyl alcohol in medicine and pharmacy: a perspective, *J. Dev. Drugs* 2 (3) (2013) 1–5.
- [40] R. Rodríguez-Rodríguez, H. Espinosa-Andrews, C. Velasquillo-Martínez, Z. Y. García-Carvajal, Composite hydrogels based on gelatin, chitosan and polyvinyl alcohol to biomedical applications: a review, *Int. J. Polym. Mater. Polym. Biomater.* 69 (1) (2020) 1–20.
- [41] M.I. Baker, S.P. Walsh, Z. Schwartz, B.D. Boyan, A review of polyvinyl alcohol and its uses in cartilage and orthopedic applications, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. B Appl. Biomater.* 100 (5) (2012) 1451–1457.
- [42] R. Wang, L. Ruan, G. Jiang, P. Li, U.E. Aharodnikau, K.E. Yunusov, X. Gao, S. O. Solomevich, Fabrication of curcumin-loaded silk fibroin and polyvinyl alcohol composite hydrogel films for skin wound healing, *ACS Appl. Bio Mater.* 5 (9) (2022) 4400–4412.
- [43] S. Thakur, M.M. Anjum, S. Jaiswal, A. Kumar, P. Deepak, S. Anand, S. Singh, P. S. Rajinikanth, Novel synergistic approach: tazarotene-calcipotriol-loaded-PVA/PVP-nanofibers incorporated in hydrogel film for management and treatment of psoriasis, *Mol. Pharm.* 20 (2) (2023) 997–1014.
- [44] L. Na, L. Zhongzhou, X. Shuguang, Dynamically formed poly (vinyl alcohol) ultrafiltration membranes with good anti-fouling characteristics, *J. Membr. Sci.* 169 (1) (2000) 17–28.
- [45] C.-c. Wang, F.-I. Yang, L.-F. Liu, Z.-m. Fu, Y. Xue, Hydrophilic and antibacterial properties of polyvinyl alcohol/4-vinylpyridine graft polymer modified polypropylene non-woven fabric membranes, *J. Membr. Sci.* 345(1–2) (2009) 223–232.
- [46] W. Yang, P. Lin, D. Cheng, L. Zhang, Y. Wu, Y. Liu, X. Pei, F. Zhou, Contribution of charges in polyvinyl alcohol networks to marine antifouling, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9 (21) (2017) 18295–18304.

- [47] J.R. Smith, D. Lamprou, C. Larson, S. Upson, Biomedical applications of polymer and ceramic coatings: a review of recent developments, *Trans. IMF* 100 (1) (2022) 25–35.
- [48] S.-H. Tang, A. Venault, L.-H. Chou, D.-H. Lan, G.V. Dizon, C. Hsieh, C.-C. Yeh, C.-L. Liu, Y. Chang, Surface PEGylation via ultrasonic spray deposition for the biofouling mitigation of biomedical interfaces, *ACS Applied Bio Materials* 5 (1) (2021) 225–234.
- [49] S. Bose, S.S. Keller, T.S. Alström, A. Boisen, K. Almdal, Process optimization of ultrasonic spray coating of polymer films, *Langmuir* 29 (23) (2013) 6911–6919.
- [50] W. Owens, Rabel and Kaelble (OWRK) method, Terms & Conditions Sitemap Print KRÜSS GmbH| Borsteler Chaussee 85 (2020) 22453.
- [51] ARCare, **Product Information Sheet**, in: ARCare 90106NB, 2017. <https://www.adhesivesresearch.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/ARcare%C2%AE-90106NB-Product-Information-Sheet-2.pdf>.
- [52] A. Jagannath, Y. Li, H. Cong, J. Hassan, G. Gonzalez, W. Wang, N. Zhang, M. D. Gilchrist, UV-assisted Hyperbranched poly (β -amino ester) modification of a silica membrane for two-step microfluidic DNA extraction from blood, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (26) (2023) 31159–31172.
- [53] M. Pulix, V. Lukashchuk, D.C. Smith, A.J. Dickson, Molecular characterization of HEK293 cells as emerging versatile cell factories, *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 71 (2021) 18–24.
- [54] J.M. Calderón-Montaño, S.M. Martínez-Sánchez, V. Jiménez-González, E. Burgos-Morón, E. Guillén-Mancina, J.J. Jiménez-Alonso, P. Díaz-Ortega, F. García, A. Aparicio, M. López-Lázaro, Screening for selective anticancer activity of 65 extracts of plants collected in Western Andalusia, Spain, *Plants* 10 (10) (2021) 2193.
- [55] S. Viswanathan, T. Palaniyandi, D.C. Chellam, M.F. Ahmed, N. Shoban, M. Pushpakumar, M.R.A. Wahab, G. Baskar, M. Ravi, A. Sivaji, Anti-cancer activity of *Hypnea valentiae* seaweed loaded gold nanoparticles through EMT signaling pathway in A549 cells, *Biochem. Syst. Ecol.* 107 (2023) 104606.
- [56] C. Garcia-de-Alba, Repurposing A549 adenocarcinoma cells: new options for drug discovery, *American Thoracic Society* (2021) 405–406.
- [57] M. Bernard, E. Jubeli, J. Bakar, J. Saunier, N. Yagoubi, Impact of simulated biological aging on physicochemical and biocompatibility properties of cyclic olefin copolymers, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 97 (2019) 377–387.
- [58] P.M. van Midwoud, A. Janse, M.T. Merema, G.M. Groothuis, E. Verpoorte, Comparison of biocompatibility and adsorption properties of different plastics for advanced microfluidic cell and tissue culture models, *Anal. Chem.* 84 (9) (2012) 3938–3944.
- [59] Y. Guan, H. Zhang, Z. Yan, X. Wei, Z. Zhang, X. Chen, Surface modification of cyclic-olefin-copolymer (COC)-based microchannels for the large-scale industrial production of droplet microfluidic devices, *Bioengineering* 10 (7) (2023) 763.
- [60] M. Mozetič, Plasma-stimulated super-hydrophilic surface finish of polymers, *Polymers* 12 (11) (2020) 2498.
- [61] Q. Du, P. Zhou, Y. Pan, X. Qu, L. Liu, H. Yu, J. Hou, Influence of hydrophobicity and roughness on the wetting and flow resistance of water droplets on solid surface: a many-body dissipative particle dynamics study, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 249 (2022) 117327.
- [62] C. Jothi Prakash, R. Prasanth, Approaches to design a surface with tunable wettability: a review on surface properties, *J. Mater. Sci.* 56 (2021) 108–135.
- [63] H. Wang, D.T. Wang, X.Y. Zhang, Z.Z. Zhang, Modified PDMS with inserted hydrophilic particles for water harvesting, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 213 (2021) 108954.
- [64] S. Konishi, C. Ohya, T. Yamada, Selective control of the contact and transport between droplet pairs by electrowetting-on-dielectric for droplet-array sandwiching technology, *Sci. Rep.* 11 (1) (2021) 12355.
- [65] M. Tenjimayashi, K. Manabe, A review on control of droplet motion based on wettability modulation: principles, design strategies, recent progress, and applications, *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.* 23 (1) (2022) 473–497.
- [66] Y. Cai, J. Hu, H. Ma, B. Yi, H. Zhang, Effects of hydrophilic/hydrophobic properties on the water behavior in the micro-channels of a proton exchange membrane fuel cell, *J. Power Sources* 161 (2) (2006) 843–848.
- [67] S. Cai, C. Wu, W. Yang, W. Liang, H. Yu, L. Liu, Recent advance in surface modification for regulating cell adhesion and behaviors, *Nanotechnol. Rev.* 9 (1) (2020) 971–989.
- [68] B. Majhy, P. Priyadarshini, A. Sen, Effect of surface energy and roughness on cell adhesion and growth–facile surface modification for enhanced cell culture, *RSC Adv.* 11 (25) (2021) 15467–15476.
- [69] D.P. Dowling, I.S. Miller, M. Ardhauoi, W.M. Gallagher, Effect of surface wettability and topography on the adhesion of osteosarcoma cells on plasma-modified polystyrene, *J. Biomater. Appl.* 26 (3) (2011) 327–347.
- [70] J.H. Lee, H.W. Jung, I.-K. Kang, H.B. Lee, Cell behaviour on polymer surfaces with different functional groups, *Biomaterials* 15 (9) (1994) 705–711.
- [71] A. Köllnberger, R. Schrader, C.A. Briehn, Carboxylic acid mediated antimicrobial activity of silicone elastomers, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 113 (2020) 111001.
- [72] M. Berenguel-Alonso, M. Sabés-Alsina, R. Morató, O. Ymbern, L. Rodríguez-Vázquez, O. Talló-Parra, J. Alonso-Chamarro, M. Puyol, M. López-Béjar, Rapid prototyping of a cyclic olefin copolymer microfluidic device for automated oocyte culturing, *SLAS TECHNOLOGY: Translating Life Sciences Innovation* 22 (5) (2017) 507–517.
- [73] M. Bernard, E. Jubeli, J. Bakar, L. Tortolano, J. Saunier, N. Yagoubi, Biocompatibility assessment of cyclic olefin copolymers: impact of two additives on cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, inflammatory reactions, and hemocompatibility, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. A* 105 (12) (2017) 3333–3349.